

EFFECTIVENESS OF COMBINED USE OF FRACTIONAL CO₂ LASER AND 595 NM PDL IN THE TREATMENT OF VARIOUS TYPES OF SCARS

Umarkhodjaye A.M.

Gulyamov S.S.,

Umarkhodjaye G.M.

Department of Plastic Surgery at the Children's Multidisciplinary
Clinic of Tashkent State Medical University,
Head of the Department of Simulation Training, Clinical Modulation,
Dentistry and Pediatric Dentistry
Department of Pharmacology, Tashkent State Medical University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17824311>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 27th November 2025

Accepted: 28th November 2025

Online: 29th November 2025

KEYWORDS

The study included 60 patients (38 women and 22 men) aged from 20 to 55 years (mean age - 36.4 ± 8.2 years) with different types of scars: hypertrophic ($n=35$), atrophic ($n=20$) and keloid ($n=5$).

ABSTRACT

Scars remain one of the most common problems in dermatology and plastic surgery. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), about 100 million people acquire scars after surgery and trauma every year [1,2]. Scar tissue can cause significant cosmetic discomfort and, in some cases, functional limitations, especially when localized in the area of joints or face [3,4]

Introduction. Scars remain one of the most common problems in dermatology and plastic surgery. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), about 100 million people acquire scars after surgery and trauma every year [1,2]. Scar tissue can cause significant cosmetic discomfort and, in some cases, functional limitations, especially when localized in the area of joints or face [3,4].

Material and Methods. The study included 60 patients (38 women and 22 men) aged from 20 to 55 years (mean age - 36.4 ± 8.2 years) with different types of scars: hypertrophic ($n=35$), atrophic ($n=20$) and keloid ($n=5$). The duration of scarring ranged from 6 months to 5 years. Patients had no acute inflammatory skin diseases and systemic contraindications to laser treatment. Patients were treated at RS laser clinic between 2022 and 2025.

Results. The study included 60 patients who underwent combined treatment of scars using fractional CO₂ laser and 595 nm PDL followed by treatment with tacrolimus ointment. Analysis of clinical parameters showed statistically significant improvement 6 months after completion of therapy. The mean visual analog scale (VAS) redness decreased from 7.2 ± 1.1 to 1.9 ± 0.7 ($p < 0.001$). Scar height decreased from 2.1 ± 0.4 mm to 1.15 ± 0.3 mm ($p < 0.001$), and scar tissue volume decreased by 45% (from 1.8 ± 0.5 cm³ to 0.99 ± 0.4 cm³; $p < 0.001$). Significant improvement in skin texture (by $38 \pm 7\%$, $p < 0.05$) indicates qualitative remodeling of the dermis under the influence of combined laser treatment.

Conclusion. The results obtained confirm the high efficacy and safety of combined therapy using fractional CO₂ laser and 595 nm PDL in the treatment of scars. Statistical

analysis demonstrates a significant correlation between laser exposure parameters and clinical improvements, which allows recommending individual selection of parameters to maximize the therapeutic effect. High patient satisfaction and low incidence of side effects emphasize the clinical applicability of this technique.

References:

- 1.Singer AJ, Clark RA. Cutaneous wound healing. N Engl J Med. 1999;341(10):738-746.
- 2.Mustoe TA, Cooter RD, Gold MH, et al. International clinical recommendations on scar management. Plast Reconstr Surg. 2002;110(2):560-571.
- 3.Manuskiatti W, Fitzpatrick RE. Treatment response of keloidal and hypertrophic sternotomy scars: comparison among intralesional corticosteroid, 585-nm flashlamp-pumped pulsed-dye laser, and combined treatment. Arch Dermatol. 2002;138(9):1149-1155.
- 4.Hantash BM, Bedi VP, Kapadia B, et al. In vivo histologic evaluation of a novel ablative fractional resurfacing device. Lasers Surg Med. 2007;39(2):96-107.

